

A Study of Quranic Approach to Spiritual Development

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Abstract

The objective of this investigation is to explore and elucidate the Quranic standpoint on the spiritual advancement of man. The aim is to comprehend the meaning and essence of spiritual development, establish its foundation, and derive measurable indicators. A comprehensive understanding of the Quranic perspective unveils fundamental principles and values embedded in Islamic spiritual concepts, influencing an individual's spiritual attributes. This, in turn, contributes to a heightened awareness, thoughtfulness, and consciousness of Allah in a Muslim's words and actions, fostering effective development. The reciprocal relationship between the Divine and human beings is deemed a crucial Islamic value in spiritual discourse. The Quranic narratives furnish an extensive definition of the concept of spiritual development and conduct a conceptual analysis of spiritual care within an Islamic framework. This paper references specific examples that aptly illustrate the Quranic viewpoint on the spiritual development of man.

Key Words: Spirituality, Devine, Mutual relationship, Islamic Spirituality, Spiritual consciousness,

Introduction

The Quran stands as the primary and unparalleled source of Islamic Spirituality. It provides a comprehensive outlook on "spirituality," intertwining it seamlessly with everyday activities. In Islam, the spiritual dimension encompasses all aspects of life, rendering everything 'spiritual'

when aligned with Allah's satisfaction. According to Islamic teachings, humanity comprises two core elements: the visible body and the vital soul, referred to as 'ruh' in Arabic, signifying Spirit. This pertains to matters related to or impacting the human spirit or soul, rather than material or physical aspects. In the Islamic perspective, as articulated by Sayyed Hossein Nasr, the Spirit permeates everything that unveils the One and guides towards the One. The ultimate purpose of Islam is to disclose the Unity of the Divine Principle and harmonize the diverse world in the light of that Unity. Spirituality in Islam is indivisible from an awareness of the One, Allah, and a life led in accordance with His Will. The core principle of Unity (al-tawḥīd) resides at the core of the Islamic message, shaping Islamic spirituality in its diverse dimensions and manifestations¹.

This finds expression in the *Quran*² as the Allah is the source of inspiration to man that creates a quest of consciousness of spirituality giving birth to what we call as Islamic Spirituality. Indeed, this can be considered as an alternative term for the realization of Allah's presence. The principles outlined in the Quran guide individuals towards unity and prevent the scattering and dispersion of the soul. It is accurate to assert that spirituality involves the utilization of intellect, inclinations, and capabilities to cultivate an awareness of the origin of the universe. This encompasses worshipping God, seeking His satisfaction, practicing humility, submission, and trust, all of which should manifest in every action undertaken by an individual.³ Another definition characterizes spirituality as a purposeful and meaningful state of human life, stemming from belief in the infinite power and perfections of God, as well as faith in life after death. The state of spiritual health contributes to happiness, hope, satisfaction, confidence, comfort, and salvation, both in the present world and the hereafter. The Quran delineates various aspects of the spiritual path, emphasizing the importance of aligning one's life with these principles for holistic well-being⁴.

Quran mentions different terminologies which depict the ways for spiritual development of the man. Some of the terms have been discussed as following:

Tafakkur and Tadabbur

Man possesses a dual nature, necessitating continuous provision for both physical and spiritual sustenance in order to thrive. The Quran delineates the earthly realm (Al-Quran: 14:32) as the focal point for acquiring physical provisions, while spiritual sustenance emanates from the

'Being of Allah.' Referred to as 'Lord's sustenance' (Al-Quran: 20:131), spiritual provision essentially results from a connection with the divine source of sustenance, namely Allah. The attainment of this objective hinges entirely on mental actions, specifically through the Quranic concepts of tafakkur and tadabbur, also known as contemplation or remembrance of Allah. These mental processes serve as the foundation for experiencing spirituality or Ruhaniyyat in Islam. It is crucial to recognize that the Quran emphasizes contemplation (tafakkur and tadabbur) as the initial step in all spiritual endeavors..⁵

Tazkiyah: It means abandoning a life of ignorance and wretchedness and leading a life ruled by the conscience. The personal realization of Allah .

The *Qur'an* says,

“*Tazkiyah* alone can lead one to Heaven”⁶

And,

“Before descending to Earth, all human beings entered into a covenant with Allah, pledging to worship Him exclusively⁷. *Tazkiyah*, or purification, signifies the fulfillment and restoration of the initial agreement between humans and Allah. Every human soul made a covenant with Allah before its creation, committing to obey Him. The commission of sins by humans is a breach of this covenant. *Tazkiyah*, as a transformative process, aids individuals in adhering to their part of the covenant.”⁸

Dhikr: Dhikr, meaning 'remembrance' or 'mentioning' of Allah, serves as the pathway to cultivating Divine consciousness. According to Quranic instructions (18:28; 33:41), Dhikr involves the frequent repetition of Allah's Names, to be recited individually, such as following each of the five daily prayers or collectively as a community⁹. Upon achieving this heightened state of consciousness, an individual remains in a perpetual state of Dhikr, even when specific words may not be uttered. The Quran consistently emphasizes the importance of remembering Allah, known as Dhikrullah, urging believers to engage in it frequently.

The act of remembering Allah becomes an expression of divine feelings, love, and praise, manifesting in verbal articulation, thus constituting Dhikr. This practice aligns with Quranic injunctions and represents a practical manifestation of spiritual attainment. Remembrance, as

highlighted in the Quran, serves as a robust support on the journey towards Allah, forming the very foundation of the spiritual path [10]. The Quranic verse asserts, "It is only in the remembrance of Allah that hearts are comforted" ¹⁰.

Allah encourages believers with the directive, "O you who believe, make remembrance of Allah abundantly" ¹¹. The Prophet, exemplifying this principle, seamlessly integrated the remembrance of Allah into every aspect of life, blurring the distinction between Dhikrullah and other activities. Thus, for the Prophet, remembering Allah was not a separate endeavor but rather intricately interwoven into every task ¹².

Taqwa: Taqwa, translated as "fear of Allah," encompasses the practical expression of faith in one's daily life, involving the avoidance of forbidden actions and a willingness to follow Allah's commands. It entails discerning between what is lawful and unlawful, right and wrong, and good and bad. Taqwa serves as the amalgamation of all virtues, with its essence lying in safeguarding oneself from Allah's punishment through obedience. This concept is encapsulated in the statement, "so-and-so protected himself with his shield" ¹³. The Quran reinforces the significance of Taqwa, asserting, "Verily the noblest of you in the sight of Allah is the one who is the most Allah-fearing" ¹⁴.

Khawf, meaning fear of Allah, is underscored by the Prophet's declaration that one who weeps out of fear of Allah will be spared from the fire. Moreover, the dust from the path of Allah will not mix with the servant's nostrils alongside the smoke of Hell. Anas b. Malik relayed the Prophet's insight, stating, "If you knew what I know, you would laugh little and cry much."

Abu 'Ali ad-Daqqaq delineated various stages of Khawf, categorizing it as Khawf, Khashya, and Haybah (fear, dread, and awe). Khawf is considered a condition of faith and its criterion, as Allah instructs believers to "Fear Me if you are believers" ¹⁵. Khashya, on the other hand, is associated with outer knowledge, as indicated by the Quranic verse, "Truly they fear Allah, among His servants, who are learned" ¹⁶.

Tawbah, or repentance, is emphasized in the Quran, urging believers to turn collectively toward God for attaining bliss¹⁷. Anas b. Malik reported the Prophet's teaching that the one who repents from sin is akin to one without sin, and God's love for a servant prevents sin from adhering to him. This sentiment is echoed in the Quran, stating, "Verily God loves those who turn unto Him [in repentance], and He loves those who purify themselves."¹⁸

Spiritual Training Techniques in Islam:

Islam provides a framework for spiritual development through five pillars that serve as practical manifestations of faith (Iman). These pillars are discussed briefly as follows:

Salah (Prayer): Salah brings individuals into communion with Allah five times a day, fostering remembrance, reinforcing fear, cultivating love, and reminding believers of divine commands. Congregational prayers are emphasized to prepare the entire community for the journey of spiritual development.

Sawm (Fasting): Fasting for a month each year trains individuals and the Muslim community in righteousness and self-restraint. It provides an opportunity for both the rich and the poor to experience hunger, preparing them to endure hardships in their pursuit of pleasing Allah.¹⁹

Zakah (Charity): Zakah develops a sense of monetary sacrifice, sympathy, and cooperation among Muslims. It is not merely a tax but a means of uplifting and purifying the soul. The spirit of Zakah emphasizes sublimity and purification through selfless monetary assistance to brethren²⁰.

Hajj (Pilgrimage): Hajj aims at fostering universal brotherhood among the faithful, grounded in the worship of Allah. It engenders a global movement that has responded to the call of Truth throughout the centuries, perpetuating this response for eternity²¹.

Concept of Ihsan: *Ihsan* means "Perfection", Excellence". It Is an Arabic word which means God consciousness. It also means protection and shield from what is harmful It is a

matter of taking one's inner faith (*Iman*) and showing it in both deed and action, a sense of social responsibility borne from religious convictions.²² Its meaning "to do beautiful things", is one of the three dimensions of the Islamic religion: *Islam*, *Iman* and *Ihsan*. One who "does what is beautiful" is called a *Muhsin*.²³ It is generally held that a person can only achieve true *Ihsan* with the help and guidance of Allah, who governs all things is described in the tradition by the Prophet (SAW) as:

The Holy Prophet Muhammad (SAW) said, *Ihsan* is:

"That you should Worship Allah, that you should live for Allah, as though you are seeing Him."²⁴

It signifies that man has attained highest excellence in words, deeds and thoughts, identifying his will with the will of Allah and harmonizing it, to the best of his knowledge and ability, with the Divine will. He thus begins to like what is liked by the Lord and to dislike what He dislikes. Man should then not only avoid evil, for it displeases his Lord, but should use all his powers to eradicate it from the face of the earth; he should not be content with adorning himself with the good which Allah wants to flourish but should also strive to attain and propagate it in the world, even at the cost of his life. A man who reaches this stage attains the highest pinnacle of Spirituality and is nearest to Allah.²⁵

Conclusion:

In summary, Islamic spirituality, rooted in the Quran, integrates the material and spiritual aspects of life, emphasizing unity through faith and alignment with Allah's will. The Quran serves as a guiding light, symbolized in the verse describing Allah as the light of the heavens and the earth. Spiritual development is facilitated through concepts such as Tafakkur, Tadabbur, Tazkiyah, Dhikr, Taqwa, Khawf, Tawbah, and the five pillars of Islam. These pillars, including Salah, Sawm, Zakah, Hajj, and the concept of Ihsan, form the practical manifestation of spiritual training, fostering individual and collective growth, leading to the highest pinnacle of spirituality and closeness to Allah. In short, the spiritual dimension of Islam can strengthen the faith and provides variety of to treat, cure and develop Muslims' spirituality in particular and whole

humanity in general. It is the only way Islam that provides a variety of ways to treat, cure and develop a growing spiritual Muslims today.

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